

Possibility of Proving $P = NP$ through 3-Partition Problems

Glenn Patrick King Ang

Abstract

The P versus NP problem is a very intriguing concept as it asks whether difficult problems have an alternative easier solution, but the difficulty of a problem usually only exist from the perspective of the solver.

This paper details an alternative method to efficiently solve a 3-partition problem, which is considered a strongly NP-complete problem. Thus, proving that there exists an efficient method to solve a 3-partition problem might also prove $P = NP$.

Section 2 provides the logic behind the algorithm that efficiently solves a 3-partition problem. Section 3 provides proof of the algorithm's efficiency by only taking 10 steps using an equation and a logic condition to find all possible subsets when given a set containing 27 elements. Section 4 provides additional proof by only taking 3 steps to find all possible subsets of a set containing 6 elements. Section 5 provides an overview of the algorithm used in this experiment and its limitations as a proof of concept.

Section 6 provides a detailed step by step application of the logic used by the algorithm using the set given on section 4. Section 7, 8, 9, and 10 details the solution implemented when the algorithm encounters special cases where multiple possible combinations exist. Section 11, 12, and 13 discusses the possibility of proving $P = NP$ in the future through 3- partition problems. Additionally, section 14 provides a direct comparison of the results between a complete greedy algorithm and the proposed efficient algorithm.

1. Introduction

The 3-partition problem is a great example of a strongly NP-complete problem because finding each subset is a lot harder and more time consuming than verifying the sum of each subset.

The 3-partition problem:

- a. Given a set of numbers, find all the possible subsets with three elements each
- b. The sum of each subset must all have the same value

2. Logic behind the algorithm for solving 3-partition problems

The main idea behind the algorithm for quickly solving the 3-partition problem is efficiency through the immediate reduction of the set. Once a subset is identified, it is immediately removed from the main set of numbers, which makes it possible to attain near instantaneous results without having to go through each number one by one.

Furthermore, logic dictates that the largest number will only be able to add up with the smallest number, thus sorting the list ascendingly will immediately allow the algorithm to find the perfect match for each subset. Looking for these combinations early on can greatly reduce the steps it takes to find all the remaining subsets.

Applying all of these concepts in the algorithm for the 3-partition problem resulted in fewer steps to identify the exact match for every subset containing three elements each that equates to the same value of sum as all the other possible subsets.

3. Proof of the algorithm's efficiency

set_of_numbers = [20, 23, 25, 30, 49, 45, 27, 30, 30, 40, 23, 18, 55,
35, 0, 89, 1, 0, 45, 40, 5, 0, -1, 91, -89, 179, 0,]

set sorted: [-89, -1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 5, 18, 20, 23, 23, 25, 27, 30, 30, 30, 35, 40, 40, 45, 45, 49, 55, 89, 91, 179]

Number of subsets: 9

Total sum = 810

Amount each subset = 90

=====

the difference: $0 = 90 - (179 + -89)$

the difference: $0 = 90 - (91 + -1)$

the difference: $1 = 90 - (89 + 0)$

the difference: $35 = 90 - (55 + 0)$

the difference: $36 = 90 - (49 + 5)$

the difference: $23 = 90 - (49 + 18)$

the difference: $40 = 90 - (45 + 5)$

the difference: $25 = 90 - (45 + 20)$

the difference: $27 = 90 - (40 + 23)$

Sum of Remaining subset: [30, 30, 30] = 90

=====

The complete list: [[0, 179, -89], [0, 91, -1], [1, 89, 0], [35, 55, 0], [23, 49, 18], [40, 45, 5], [25, 45, 20], [27, 40, 23], [30, 30, 30]]

The amount for each subset is: 90

Total steps for all the functions to complete: 20

Total steps for finding a match for all the subsets: 10

4. Further Proof: Given set

set_of_numbers = [7, 2, 5, 1, 7, 8]

set sorted: [1, 2, 5, 7, 7, 8]

Number of subsets: 2

Total sum = 30

Amount each subset = 15

=====

the difference: $6 = 15 - (8 + 1)$

the difference: $5 = 15 - (8 + 2)$

Sum of Remaining subset: [1, 7, 7] = 15

=====

The complete list: [[5, 8, 2], [1, 7, 7]]

The amount for each subset is: 15

Total steps for all the functions to complete: 6

Total steps for finding a match for all the subsets: 3

5. The algorithm for the 3-partition problems

The algorithm was created as a proof of concept; thus, it only works when the sum of each subset is positive. Some changes have to be made to the mathematical equation if it is to work when the sum of each subset is negative.

Furthermore, the algorithm was not fully tested for all possible bugs, thus errors might occur for instances that have not been originally anticipated. Only three special cases were anticipated where error might occur:

- a. There are two possible correct combination for a given number, but only one combination is acceptable. See section 7 for this special case.

Given the Set = [0, 7, 2, 3, 1, 9, 8, 5, 1]

- 9 has two possible combinations: [9, 3, 0] and [9, 2, 1]
 - 8 only has one combination: [8, 3, 1]
- b. The sum of each subset has the same value, but a large number doesn't have a match. See section 8 for this special case.
- c. The sum of each subset has the same value. There are two possible correct combinations, but only one can form a subset. See section 9 for this special case.
- d. The sum of each subset has the same value. There are multiple possible combinations (based on the problem shown in section 7: Special Case A). See section 10 for this special case.

The computer program used for this experiment was created using the python programming language. See python code in Appendix A.

6. Applying the logic of the algorithm manually

The steps shown in this section only replicates the general process that the algorithm uses to efficiently find the correct combinations for each subset. These steps do not fully reflect the other logical operators and conditions that were used in the python code.

Applying the logic of the algorithm manually using the same set given in section 4:

Given the set = [7, 2, 5, 1, 7, 8]

Step 1. Is the number of elements inside the set evenly divisible by 3?

If not, terminate the program

If yes, divide the number of elements inside the set by 3

Answer: Yes

- $\text{number_of_elements} = 6$
- $\text{number_of_subsets} = \text{number_of_elements} / 3$
 $\text{number_of_subsets} = 6 / 3 = 2$

Step 2. Get the sum of all the elements inside the set

- $\text{Sum} = 7 + 2 + 5 + 1 + 7 + 8 = 30$

Step 3. Is the sum evenly divisible by the number of subsets?

If not, terminate the program

If yes, get the amount for each subset

Answer: Yes

- amount per subset = sum / number_of_subsets
- amount per subset = $30 / 2 = 15$

Step 4. Sort ascendingly

- Set = [1, 2, 5, 7, 7, 8]

Step 5. Use the mathematical formula:

- difference = amount_per_subset – (largest_number + smallest_number)
- difference = $15 - (8 + 1) = 15 - 9 = 6$

Step 6. Check if the difference is inside the set

If not, move on to the next smallest number (step 7)

If yes, proceed to step 9

Answer: No

Step 7. Proceeding with the next smallest number

- difference = $15 - (8 + 2) = 15 - 10 = 5$

Step 8. Same instructions as Step 6

Check if the difference is inside the set

If not, move on to the next smallest number (step 7)

If yes, proceed to step 9

Answer: Yes, 5 is inside the set

Step 9. Collect all three numbers and store it

- Largest number: 8
Smallest number: 2
Difference: 5
- collect_numbers = [8, 2, 5]

Step 10. Delete the collected numbers from the original set

- set = [1, 2, 5, 7, 7, 8]
- delete [8, 2, 5]

- new_set = [1, 7, 7]

Step 11. Is there more than 1 subset remaining?

If yes, start over from step 5 with the new_set of numbers

If no, proceed to step 12

Answer: No

Step 12. Is the sum of all the elements inside the new_set equates to amount_per_subset?

If no, terminate the program

If yes, store the three numbers

Answer: Yes, because $7 + 7 + 1 = 15$

Step 13. Output final subsets

- Subsets = [8, 2, 5] and [1, 7, 7]
- Original sorted set = [1, 2, 5, 7, 7, 8]

Output: Total steps for finding a match for all the subsets: 3

7. Special case A: There are two possible combinations, but only one specific combination is acceptable

Set = [0, 7, 2, 3, 1, 9, 8, 5, 1]

Sum = 36

Number of subsets = 3

Amount each subset = 12

Following the logic of the algorithm, the algorithm will output an error because of the following:

- 9 has two possible combinations: [9, 3, 0] and [9, 2, 1]
- 8 only has one combination: [8, 3, 1]
- The only acceptable combination is: [9, 2, 1], [8, 3, 1], and [0, 7, 5]

Starting the steps:

Step 1. Is the number of elements inside the set evenly divisible by 3?

If not, terminate the program

If yes, divide the number of elements inside the set by 3

Answer: Yes

- $\text{number_of_elements} = 9$
- $\text{number_of_subsets} = \text{number_of_elements} / 3$
- $\text{number_of_subsets} = 9 / 3 = 3$

Step 2. Get the sum of all the elements inside the set

- $\text{Sum} = 0 + 7 + 2 + 3 + 1 + 9 + 8 + 5 + 1 = 36$

Step 3. Is the sum evenly divisible by the number of subsets?

If not, terminate the program

If yes, get the amount for each subset

Answer: Yes

- $\text{amount per subset} = \text{sum} / \text{number_of_subsets}$
- $\text{amount per subset} = 36 / 3 = 12$

Step 4. Sort ascendingly

- $\text{Set} = [0, 1, 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 8, 9]$

Step 5. Use the mathematical formula:

- $\text{difference} = \text{amount_per_subset} - (\text{largest_number} + \text{smallest_number})$
- $\text{difference} = 12 - (9 + 0) = 3$

Step 6. Check if the difference is inside the set

If not, move on to the next smallest number (step 7)

If yes, proceed to step 9

Answer: Yes, the difference is in the set

Step 9. Collect all three numbers and store it

- Largest number: 9
- Smallest number: 0
- Difference: 3

- collect_numbers = [9, 3, 0]

Step 10. Delete the collected numbers from the original set

- set = [0, 1, 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 8, 9]
- delete [9, 3, 0]

- new_set = [1, 1, 2, 5, 7, 8]

Step 11. Is there more than 1 subset remaining?

If yes, start over from step 5 with the new_set of numbers

If no, proceed to the next step

Answer: Yes

Step 5. The next number is 8

- 8 will not have a perfect match because 3 was already taken by 9
- The only possible set for 8 to have a combined sum of 12 is:
 - [8, 3, 1]
- 9 has two possible combinations to have a combined sum of 12:
 - [9, 3, 0] and [9, 1, 2]

Since the smallest number is 0 and the difference between 12 and 9 is in the set, this combination was prioritized by the algorithm. Now, instead of having a subset of both [9, 1, 2] and [8, 3, 1], it resulted into the termination of the program.

Solution: The solution was already implemented in the python code.

Step A. Implement a conditional statement:

Once the smallest_number reaches the middle of the set and there is still no match, the program should be restarted only if there are already other subsets found.

Step B. Restore the set back to its original sorted form

- Set = [0, 1, 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 8, 9]

Step C. Restart the algorithm, but start at the number where the error occurred

- Start from Step 5 with 8 as the starting number.

This ensures that if there are two possible combinations for a number, but only one is acceptable, then the algorithm restarts to adapt to the new problem where the current number doesn't have a match.

Step 5. Use the mathematical formula:

- $\text{difference} = \text{amount_per_subset} - (\text{largest_number} + \text{smallest_number})$
- $\text{difference} = 12 - (8 + 0) = 4$

Step 6. Check if the difference is inside the set

If not, move on to the next smallest number (step 7)

If yes, proceed to step 9

Answer: No

Step 7. Proceeding with the next smallest number

- $\text{difference} = 12 - (8 + 1) = 3$

Step 8. Same instructions as Step 6

Check if the difference is inside the set

If not, move on to the next smallest number (step 7)

If yes, proceed to step 9

Answer: Yes

Step 9. Collect all three numbers and store it

- Largest number: 8
Smallest number: 1
Difference: 3
- $\text{collect_numbers} = [8, 1, 3]$

Step 10. Delete the collected numbers from the original set

- $\text{set} = [0, 1, 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 8, 9]$
- $\text{delete } [8, 1, 3]$
- $\text{new_set} = [0, 1, 2, 5, 7, 9]$

Step 11. Is there more than 1 subset remaining?

If yes, start over from step 5 with the new_set of numbers

If no, proceed to the next step

Answer: Yes

Step 5. Use the mathematical formula:

- $\text{difference} = \text{amount_per_subset} - (\text{largest_number} + \text{smallest_number})$
- $\text{difference} = 12 - (9 + 0) = 3$

Step 6. Check if the difference is inside the set

If not, move on to the next smallest number (step 7)

If yes, proceed to step 9

Answer: No

Step 7. Proceeding with the next smallest number

- $\text{difference} = 12 - (9 + 1) = 2$

Step 8. Same instructions as Step 6

Check if the difference is inside the set

If not, move on to the next smallest number (step 7)

If yes, proceed to step 9

Answer: Yes

Step 9. Collect all three numbers and store it

- Largest number: 9
Smallest number: 1
Difference: 2
- $\text{collect_numbers} = [9, 1, 2]$

Step 10. Delete the collected numbers from the original set

- $\text{set} = [0, 1, 2, 5, 7, 9]$
- $\text{delete} [9, 1, 2]$
- $\text{new_set} = [0, 5, 7]$

Step 11. Is there more than 1 subset remaining?

If yes, start over from step 5 with the new_set of numbers

If no, proceed to step 12

Answer: No

Step 12. Is the sum of all the elements inside the new_set equates to amount_per_subset?

If no, terminate the program

If yes, store the three numbers

Answer: Yes, because $0 + 5 + 7 = 12$

Step 13. Output final subsets

- Subsets = [8, 1, 3], [9, 1, 2], and [0, 5, 7]
- Original sorted set = [0, 1, 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 8, 9]

Output: Total steps for finding a match for all the subsets: 8

8. Special case B: The sum of each subset has the same value, but a large number doesn't have a match

Set = [13, 10, 1, 8, 1, 1]

Sum = 34

Number of subsets = 2

Amount each subset = 17

Following the logic of the algorithm, the algorithm will output an error because of the following:

The sum of each subset is 17, but 13 does not have any numbers to combine with to form a subset with three elements that has a total sum value of 17.

Solution:

Step A. Implement a conditional statement:

Once the smallest_number reaches the middle of the set and there is still no match for the large number, the program can be safely terminated if no other subsets were already found.

Starting the steps:

Step 1. Is the number of elements inside the set evenly divisible by 3?

If not, terminate the program

If yes, divide the number of elements inside the set by 3

Answer: Yes

- $\text{number_of_elements} = 6$
- $\text{number_of_subsets} = \text{number_of_elements} / 3$
- $\text{number_of_subsets} = 6 / 3 = 2$

Step 2. Get the sum of all the elements inside the set

- $\text{Sum} = 13 + 10 + 1 + 8 + 1 + 1 = 34$

Step 3. Is the sum evenly divisible by the number of subsets?

If not, terminate the program

If yes, get the amount for each subset

Answer: Yes

- $\text{amount per subset} = \text{sum} / \text{number_of_subsets}$
- $\text{amount per subset} = 34 / 2 = 17$

Step 4. Sort ascendingly

- $\text{Set} = [1, 1, 1, 8, 10, 13]$

Step 5. Use the mathematical formula:

- $\text{difference} = \text{amount_per_subset} - (\text{largest_number} + \text{smallest_number})$
- $\text{difference} = 17 - (13 + 1) = 3$

Step 6. Check if the difference is inside the set

If not, move on to the next smallest number (step 7)

If yes, proceed to step 9

Answer: No

Conditional Statement: has the smallest_number already reached the middle of the set?

If not, continue

If yes, terminate the program

Answer: No

Step 7. Proceeding with the next smallest number

- $\text{difference} = 17 - (13 + 1) = 3$

Step 8. Same instructions as Step 6

Check if the difference is inside the set

If not, move on to the next smallest number (step 7)

If yes, proceed to step 9

Answer: No

Conditional Statement: has the smallest_number already reached the middle of the set?

If not, continue

If yes, terminate the program

Answer: No

Step 7. Proceeding with the next smallest number

difference = $17 - (13 + 1) = 3$

Step 8. Same instructions as Step 6

Check if the difference is inside the set

If not, move on to the next smallest number (step 7)

If yes, proceed to step 9

Answer: No

Conditional Statement: has the smallest_number already reached the middle of the set?

If not, continue

If yes, terminate the program

Answer: Yes

Output: Error no match found for this set

9. Special case C: The sum of each subset has the same value. There are two possible combinations, but only one can form a subset.

Set = [0, 0, 2, 3, 5, 9, 20, 21, 30]

Sum = 90

Number of subsets = 3

Amount each subset = 30

Following the logic of the algorithm, the algorithm will output an error because of the following:

- The only possible combination for 30 is: [0, 0, 30]
- The only possible combination for 21 is: [0, 9, 21]

There are only two 0 in the set, which prevents one of the numbers from forming a subset with three elements that has a total sum value of 30. Since the python code in Appendix A already implemented the solutions proposed for both section 7 and 8, the algorithm will first find a subset for 30, then proceed with finding a subset for 21. Once the algorithm cannot find a match for 21, it will then restart over with 21 as the initial large number. As soon as it finds a match, it will then proceed with 30 as the next large number, but the algorithm will never be able to find a possible combination for this number to form another subset.

Solution: Same as section 7 and 8. The solution was already implemented in the python code.

Step A. Implement a conditional statement:

Once the `smallest_number` reaches the middle of the set and there is still no match, the program should be restarted only if there are already other subsets found.

Step B. Restore the set to back to its original sorted form

- Set = [0, 0, 2, 3, 5, 9, 20, 21, 30]

Step C. Restart the algorithm, but start at the number where the error occurred

- Start from Step 5 with 21 as the starting number.

Step D. Implement a conditional statement:

Once the program has already been restarted and the `smallest_number` reaches the middle of the set, but there is still no match found for a specific large number, then the program can be safely terminated.

10. Special Case D: The sum of each subset has the same value. There are multiple possible combinations (based on the problem shown in section 7: Special Case A).

Set = [0, 7, 2, 3, 1, 9, 8, 5, 1, 0, 7, 2, 3, 1, 9, 8, 5, 1,]

Sorted set = [0, 0, 1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 2, 3, 3, 5, 5, 7, 7, 8, 8, 9, 9]

Sum = 72

Number of subsets = 6

Amount each subset = 12

Possible combinations:

- [9, 0, 3] [9, 0, 3] [0, 7, 5] [0, 7, 5] [8, 1, 3] [8, 1, 3] [8, 2, 2] [9, 1, 2] [9, 1, 2] [7, 2, 3] [7, 2, 3]

Following the logic of the algorithm, the algorithm will output an error because of the following:

- The only possible combination for 0 is:
 - [0, 7, 5] [0, 7, 5], instead of [9, 0, 3] [9, 0, 3]
- The only possible combination for 2 is:
 - [9, 1, 2] [9, 1, 2], instead of [8, 2, 2]
- The only possible combination for 3 is:
 - [8, 1, 3] [8, 1, 3], instead of [7, 2, 3] [7, 2, 3] [9, 0, 3] [9, 0, 3]

Result:

- The complete list: [[1, 3, 8], [1, 3, 8], [1, 2, 9], [1, 2, 9], [0, 5, 7], [0, 5, 7]]
- The amount for each subset is: 12
- Total steps for all the functions to complete: 49
- Total steps for only finding a match for all the subsets: 22

Solution: Working on top of the solutions from sections 7, 8, and 9.

The solution was already implemented in the python code: 3partition_v_2.py.

Step A. Implement a conditional statement:

Once the smallest_number reaches the middle of the set and there is still no match, the program should be restarted if there are already other subsets found.

Step B. Restore the set to back to its original sorted form

- Set = [0, 0, 1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 2, 3, 3, 5, 5, 7, 7, 8, 8, 9, 9]

Step C. Restart the algorithm, but start at the number where the error occurred

- Start from Step 5 with 7 as the starting number.

Step D. Implement a conditional statement:

Once the program has already been restarted and the `smallest_number` reaches the middle of the set, but there is still no match found for a specific large number, then the program can be safely terminated.

Step E. Create another list that will contain the combinations after the restart:

Once the program has already been restarted and a match was found for the number that caused an error, store the combination inside the `restart_set_collected`. The `restart_set_collected` ensures that if another number cannot find a match and have to restart, every number in the `restart_set_collected` is going to be excluded when the set is restored back to the original set.

11. Complexity of the 3-partition problem

It is quite challenging to come up with different set of numbers that contains unique problems that the algorithm is simply not able to solve. Additional unique sets of numbers are required to be able to further improve the algorithm in order to solve all possible 3-partition problems more efficiently.

12. Future of the algorithm

Further improvements on the algorithm might one day be able to solve all of the possible 3-partition problems.

13. Possibility of proving $P = NP$ through 3-Partition Problems

(“Partition problem,” 2021) stated that $P = NP$ if a pseudo-polynomial time algorithm exists for 3-partition problems. Therefore, if this statement is true, then it might be possible in the future to prove that $P = NP$ using the algorithm proposed in this paper.

The algorithm in the 3partition.py heavily relies on the built-in `list.sort()` function of the python language. Further improvements were made on the algorithm in 3partition_v_2.py and now has its own sorting algorithm, which will help determine the number of steps it takes to sort a specific set ascendingly.

Moreover, a 3partition_complete_greedy_algorithm.py was created to clearly demonstrate how many steps it will take for a complete greedy algorithm to find the correct subsets as compared to the algorithm used in 3partition_v_2.py. See python code in Appendix A and B.

14. Proposed algorithm vs. Complete greedy algorithm

A. `set_of_numbers = [9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1]`

Using 3partition_v_2.py

Original Set: [9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1]
Total number of elements inside the set: 9

Number of subsets: 3
Total sum of the entire set: 45
The amount for each subset is: 15

The complete list of subsets: [[1, 5, 9], [3, 4, 8], [2, 6, 7]]
Total steps for only finding a match for all the subsets: 4

Total steps for sorting the set (ascending): 72
Total steps for all the functions to complete: 8

Total steps for all the functions to complete + sorting: 80

Using 3partition_complete_greedy_algorithm.py

original set: [9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1]
total number of elements inside the set: 9

number of subsets: 3
Total sum of the entire set: 45
The amount for each subset is: 15

collected list of all possible subsets: [[9, 5, 1], [9, 4, 2], [8, 6, 1], [8, 5, 2], [8, 4, 3], [7, 6, 2], [7, 5, 3], [6, 5, 4]]

Total number of all possible subsets collected: 8

Total steps for finding all possible subsets: 86

***** Finding Subsets Output *****

found possible subsets: [[9, 5, 1], [9, 4, 2], [8, 6, 1], [8, 5, 2], [8, 4, 3], [7, 6, 2], [7, 5, 3], [6, 5, 4]]

The complete list of subsets: [[9, 5, 1], [8, 4, 3], [7, 6, 2]]

total steps for finding the complete list of subsets only: 5

total steps for finding all possible subsets: 86

total steps for finding all possible subsets + finding the 3 subset(s): 91

B. set_of_numbers = [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9]

Using 3partition_v_2.py

Original Set: [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9]

Total number of elements inside the set: 9

Number of subsets: 3

Total sum of the entire set: 45

The amount for each subset is: 15

The complete list of subsets: [[1, 5, 9], [3, 4, 8], [2, 6, 7]]

Total steps for only finding a match for all the subsets: 4

Total steps for sorting the set (ascending): 8

Total steps for all the functions to complete: 8

Total steps for all the functions to complete + sorting: 16

Using 3partition_complete_greedy_algorithm.py

original set: [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9]

total number of elements inside the set: 9

number of subsets: 3

Total sum of the entire set: 45

The amount for each subset is: 15

collected list of all possible subsets: [[1, 5, 9], [1, 6, 8], [2, 4, 9], [2, 5, 8], [2, 6, 7], [3, 4, 8], [3, 5, 7], [4, 5, 6]]

total number of all possible subsets collected: 8

```
total steps for finding all possible subsets: 86

***** Finding Subsets Output *****

found possible subsets: [[1, 5, 9], [1, 6, 8], [2, 4, 9], [2, 5, 8], [2, 6, 7], [3, 4, 8], [3, 5, 7], [4, 5, 6]]

The complete list of subsets: [[1, 5, 9], [2, 6, 7], [3, 4, 8]]
total steps for finding the complete list of subsets only: 5

total steps for finding all possible subsets: 86
total steps for finding all possible subsets + finding the 3 subset(s): 91
```

C. set_of_numbers = [9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1]

Using 3partition_v_2.py

```
Total number of elements inside the set: 81

Number of subsets: 27
Total sum of the entire set: 405
The amount for each subset is: 15

The complete list of subsets: [[1, 5, 9], [1, 5, 9], [1, 5, 9], [1, 5, 9], [1, 5, 9], [1, 5, 9], [1, 5, 9], [1, 5, 9], [1, 5, 9], [3, 4, 8], [3, 4, 8], [3, 4, 8], [3, 4, 8], [3, 4, 8], [3, 4, 8], [3, 4, 8], [3, 4, 8], [3, 4, 8], [3, 4, 8], [2, 6, 7], [2, 6, 7], [2, 6, 7], [2, 6, 7], [2, 6, 7], [2, 6, 7], [2, 6, 7], [2, 6, 7]]
Total steps for only finding a match for all the subsets: 36

Total steps for sorting the set (ascending): 5840
Total steps for all the functions to complete: 136

Total steps for all the functions to complete + sorting: 5976
```

Using 3partition_complete_greedy_algorithm.py

```
total number of elements inside the set: 81

number of subsets: 27
Total sum of the entire set: 405
The amount for each subset is: 15

collected list of all possible subsets: [[9, 5, 1], [9, 5, 1], . . . , [6, 5, 4]]

total number of all possible subsets collected: 7212
```


collected list of all possible subsets: [[1, 5, 9], [1, 5, 9], . . . , [4, 5, 6]]

total number of all possible subsets collected: 7212

total steps for finding all possible subsets: 85322

***** Finding Subsets Output *****

found possible subsets: [[1, 5, 9], [1, 5, 9], . . . , [4, 5, 6]]

The complete list of subsets: [[1, 5, 9], [1, 5, 9], [1, 5, 9], [1, 5, 9], [1, 5, 9], [1, 5, 9], [1, 5, 9], [1, 5, 9], [1, 5, 9], [2, 6, 7], [2, 6, 7], [2, 6, 7], [2, 6, 7], [2, 6, 7], [2, 6, 7], [2, 6, 7], [2, 6, 7], [2, 6, 7], [2, 6, 7], [3, 4, 8], [3, 4, 8], [3, 4, 8], [3, 4, 8], [3, 4, 8], [3, 4, 8], [3, 4, 8], [3, 4, 8], [3, 4, 8], [3, 4, 8]]

total steps for finding the complete list of subsets only: 449

total steps for finding all possible subsets: 85322

total steps for finding all possible subsets + finding the 27 subset(s): 85771

E. set_of_numbers = [20, 23, 25, 30, 49, 45, 27, 30, 30, 40, 23, 18, 55, 35, 0, 89, 1, 0, 45, 40, 5, 0, -1, 91, -89, 179, 0]

- same set as section 3

Using 3partition_v_2.py

Total number of elements inside the set: 27

Number of subsets: 9

Total sum of the entire set: 810

The amount for each subset is: 90

The complete list of subsets: [[-89, 0, 179], [-1, 0, 91], [0, 1, 89], [0, 35, 55], [18, 23, 49], [5, 40, 45], [20, 25, 45], [23, 27, 40], [30, 30, 30]]

Total steps for only finding a match for all the subsets: 10

Total steps for sorting the set (ascending): 650

Total steps for all the functions to complete: 20

Total steps for all the functions to complete + sorting: 670

Using 3partition_complete_greedy_algorithm.py

total number of elements inside the set: 27

number of subsets: 9

Total sum of the entire set: 810
 The amount for each subset is: 90
 collected list of all possible subsets: [[20, 25, 45], [20, 25, 45], . . . , [-89, 179, 0]]

Total number of all possible subsets collected: 49

Total steps for finding all possible subsets: 2927

***** Finding Subsets Output *****

found possible subsets: [[20, 25, 45], [20, 25, 45], [20, 30, 40], [20, 30, 40], [20, 30, 40], [20, 30, 40], [20, 30, 40], [20, 30, 40], [23, 49, 18], [23, 27, 40], [23, 27, 40], [25, 30, 35], [25, 30, 35], [25, 30, 35], [30, 30, 30], [30, 55, 5], [49, 40, 1], [49, 23, 18], [49, 1, 40], [45, 27, 18], [45, 40, 5], [45, 0, 45], [45, 0, 45], [45, 45, 0], [45, 45, 0], [45, 40, 5], [27, 40, 23], [27, 23, 40], [27, 18, 45], [30, 55, 5], [30, 55, 5], [40, 45, 5], [55, 35, 0], [55, 35, 0], [55, 35, 0], [55, 35, 0], [0, 89, 1], [0, -1, 91], [0, -89, 179], [89, 1, 0], [89, 1, 0], [89, 1, 0], [0, -1, 91], [0, -89, 179], [45, 40, 5], [0, -1, 91], [0, -89, 179], [-1, 91, 0], [-89, 179, 0]]

The complete list of subsets: [[20, 25, 45], [23, 49, 18], [23, 27, 40], [30, 30, 30], [45, 40, 5], [55, 35, 0], [0, 89, 1], [0, -1, 91], [0, -89, 179]]

total steps for finding the complete list of subsets only: 38

total steps for finding all possible subsets: 2927
 total steps for finding all possible subsets + finding the 9 subset(s): 2965

F. set_of_numbers = [13, 10, 8, 1, 1, 1] # 13 has no match

Using 3partition_v_2.py

Total steps for sorting the set (ascending): 20
 Total steps for all the functions to complete: 7

Total steps for all the functions to complete + sorting: 27

Using 3partition_complete_greedy_algorithm.py

total number of elements inside the set: 6

number of subsets: 2
 Total sum of the entire set: 34
 The amount for each subset is: 17

collected list of all possible subsets: []

Total number of all possible subsets collected: 0

Total steps for finding all possible subsets: 22

14. Conclusion

3-partition problems are quite tedious to do manually, but with the help of simple mathematical equations, inferences, and logical reasoning, the computer algorithm was able to find the matching subsets almost instantaneously. But the algorithm itself is fairly limited in the sense that it only works on sets it was originally designed to solve. There are countless possible bugs or special cases out there waiting to be discovered that were not covered in the special case sections of this paper. Thus, all possible bugs or special cases or circumstances that might arise from solving a 3-partition problem can only be solved after it has already appeared.

The 3-partition problem is considered as one of the strongly NP-complete problem, which proves that the sum of each subset is a lot easier to determine than finding the subsets of a given set. If the algorithm provided in this paper was further improved to the extent that it can be considered as a pseudo-polynomial time algorithm for 3-partition problems, then it is safe to infer that $P = NP$.

Acknowledgements

To my parents, thank you both for your continuous love, support, and belief in me. This paper would have not been possible without both of you.

To my wife Natassia, thank you for your continuous love, understanding, support, and belief in me. Thank you for always being a constant source of inspiration to me.

Glenn Patrick King Ang

<https://github.com/07231985>

glenn.patrick.king.ang@outlook.com (preferred)

glenn.p.ang@alumni.uts.edu.au (not affiliated, only an alumni)

References

Partition problem. (2021, October 16). Wikipedia. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Partition_problem

Python Code Instructions:

- a. set_of_numbers contain the set of numbers that will be used on the 3-partition problem
- b. new lists containing a set of numbers can be created by simply typing:
 - o set_of_numbers = [input the set of numbers here]
 - o set_of_numbers = [0, 7, 2, 3, 8, 5]
- c. The “#” is like an on and off switch for each set_of_numbers
 - o To use a given set, remove the “#” in front of the set_of_numbers
 - o Insert a “#” in front of set_of_numbers if the set is not going to be used

Appendix A:

Link to the GitHub repository containing the python code used in this research paper:

<https://github.com/07231985/3partition>

filename: 3partition_v_2.py

```
# Efficient Algorithm for 3 partition problems
# research paper: Possibility of proving P = NP through 3
partition problems
# created by Glenn Patrick King Ang 10/21/2021 (edited
12/03/2021)
# email: glenn.patrick.king.ang@outlook.com (preferred)
# email: glenn.p.ang@alumni.uts.edu.au (not affiliated, only an
alumni)
# https://github.com/07231985

# this program doesn't work if the amount for each subset is
negative, a change in the equation is required
# this program was not thoroughly tested for bugs
# the main purpose of the program is to act as proof of concept

# Sample Sets:
set_of_numbers = [20, 23, 25, 30, 49, 45, 27, 30, 30, 40, 23,
18, 55,
                 35, 0, 89, 1, 0, 45, 40, 5, 0, -1, 91, -89,
179, 0, ]
# set_of_numbers = [3, 1, 1, 3, 1, 1]
# set_of_numbers = [7, 2, 5, 1, 7, 8]
# set_of_numbers = [7, 2, 3, 1, 8, 5]
# set_of_numbers = [1, 1, 1]
```

```

# set_of_numbers = [0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 2, 2, 2]
# set_of_numbers = [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, ]
# set_of_numbers = [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13,
14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21]
# set_of_numbers = [0, 9, 1, 2, 8, 2, 1, 6, 1]

# anticipated bug:
# a. 2 combinations exists, but only 1 combination is correct
# b. the sum of each subset has the same value, but a number
doesn't have a match
# c. the sum of each subset has the same value, two possible
combinations, but only one can form a subset
# d. the sum of each subset has the same value, multiple
possible combinations (based on section c)

# a. Special case A (Section 7): 2 combinations exists, but
only 1 combination is correct
# set_of_numbers = [0, 7, 2, 3, 1, 9, 8, 5, 1] # [9, 0, 3] [9,
2, 1], but only [9, 2, 1] is correct
# set_of_numbers = [0, 7, 2, 3, 1, 9, 8, 5, 1, 0, 9, 3]

# b. Special case B (Section 8): equal amount per subset, one
of the large number has no match
# set_of_numbers = [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 11] # 11 has no match
# set_of_numbers = [1, 1, 1, 9, 10, 12] # 12 has no match
# set_of_numbers = [13, 10, 1, 8, 1, 1] # 13 has no match
# set_of_numbers = [1, 2, 3, 10, 13, 21, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 15] #
21 has no match
# set_of_numbers = [0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 20, 20, 20, 30] # all of the
20 has no match

# c. Special case C (Section 9): equal amount per subset, two
possible combinations, only one can form a subset
# set_of_numbers = [1, 2, 3, 0, 9, 7, 13, 18, 25] # 18 or 25
has no match because there is only one 1
# set_of_numbers = [0, 0, 2, 3, 5, 9, 20, 21, 30] # 21 or 30
has no match because there is only two 0

# d. Special case D (Section 10): multiple possible
combinations
# set_of_numbers = [0, 7, 2, 3, 1, 9, 8, 5, 1, 0, 7, 2, 3, 1,
9, 8, 5, 1, ]

# possible combinations
# [9, 0, 3] [9, 0, 3] [0, 7, 5] [0, 7, 5] // [8, 1, 3] [8, 1,
3] [8, 2, 2] [9, 1, 2] [9, 1, 2]

```

```

# only two 0, perfect choice: [0, 7, 5] [0, 7, 5], instead of
[9, 0, 3] [9, 0, 3]
# only two 2, perfect choice: [9, 1, 2] [9, 1, 2], instead of
[8, 2, 2]
# only two 3, perfect choice: [8, 1, 3] [8, 1, 3], instead of
[7, 2, 3] [7, 2, 3] [9, 0, 3] [9, 0, 3]

# d.2. Special case D (Section 10): multiple possible
combinations
# set_of_numbers = [0, 7, 2, 3, 1, 9, 8, 5, 1, 0, 7, 2, 3, 1,
9, 8, 5, 1,
#           0, 7, 2, 3, 1, 9, 8, 5, 1, 0, 7, 2, 3, 1,
9, 8, 5, 1, ]

# no possible combinations
# set_of_numbers = [20, 5, 5, 5, 5, 10]
# set_of_numbers = [10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 40] # error
# set_of_numbers = [0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 90] # error
# set_of_numbers = [0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1]
# set_of_numbers = [0, 7, 2, 3, 8, 5]

# Random set of numbers
# set_of_numbers = [0, 0, 1, 1, 1, 1]
# set_of_numbers = [0, 0, 22, 10, 10, 0, 16, 1, 1]
# set_of_numbers = [0, 18, 2, 0, 10, 10, 2, 16, 2]
# set_of_numbers = [5, 5, 2, 6, 4, 4, 7, 3, 0]
# set_of_numbers = [0, 5, 7, 2, 6, 6, 4, 1, 5]
# set_of_numbers = [1, 0, 3, 1, 1, 9, 9, 0, 0]
# set_of_numbers = [1, 0, 3, 1, 1, 9, 9, 0, 3]
# set_of_numbers = [1, 0, 3, 1, 1, 9, 9, 0, 6]
# set_of_numbers = [15, 3, 2, 14, 5, 1, 13, 0, 7]
# set_of_numbers = [10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90]

# odd numbers
# set_of_numbers = [1, 3, 5, 7, 11, 13, 17, 19, 23]
# set_of_numbers = [1, 3, 5, 7, 11, 13, 17, 19, 23, 29, 31, 37]

# set_of_numbers = [1, 3, 5, 7, 11, 13, 17, 19, 23, 29, 31, 37,
41, 43, 47, 53,
#           59, 61, 67, 71, 73, 79, 83, 89, 97, 101,
103, 107, 109, 111 ]

# number of steps test sets (Section 14):

# section 14.a
# set_of_numbers = [9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1]

```



```

#           0, 7, 2, 3, 1, 9, 8, 5, 1, 0, 7, 2, 3, 1,
9, 8, 5, 1,
#           0, 7, 2, 3, 1, 9, 8, 5, 1, 0, 7, 2, 3, 1,
9, 8, 5, 1,
#           0, 7, 2, 3, 1, 9, 8, 5, 1]

# section 14.h
# set_of_numbers = [9, 9, 9, 9, 9, 9, 9, 9, 9, 9, 9, 9, 9, 9,
9, 9, 9, 9,
#           9, 9, 9, 8, 8, 8, 8, 8, 8, 8, 8, 8, 8, 8,
8, 8, 8, 8,
#           8, 8, 8, 8, 8, 8, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7,
7, 7, 7, 7,
#           7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5,
5, 5, 5, 5,
#           5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 3, 3,
3, 3, 3, 3,
#           3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3,
3, 2, 2, 2,
#           2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2,
2, 2, 2, 2,
#           1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1,
1, 1, 1, 1,
#           1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1,
1, 1, 1, 1,
#           1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0,
0, 0, 0, 0,
#           0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0]

# section 14.i
# set_of_numbers = [0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0,
0, 0, 0, 0,
#           0, 0, 0, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1,
1, 1, 1, 1,
#           1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1,
1, 1, 1, 1,
#           1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2,
2, 2, 2, 2,
#           2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 3, 3,
3, 3, 3, 3,
#           3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3,
3, 5, 5, 5,
#           5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5,
5, 5, 5, 5,
#           7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7,
7, 7, 7, 7,

```



```

        if set_of_numbers[x - 1] > set_of_numbers[x]:
            switch_numbers = set_of_numbers[x - 1]
            set_of_numbers[x - 1] = set_of_numbers[x]
            set_of_numbers[x] = switch_numbers
            set_complete += 1

    if set_complete == -1:
        break

    print("\n***** Sorting
Sets Results *****")
    print(f"Total steps for sorting the set (ascending) =
{count_steps_sorting}")
    print(f"Original Set = {original_set}")
    print(f"\nSorted Set = {set_of_numbers}")

print("*****")

def restart_match(number):
    global new_set_numbers
    global loop_count
    global break_all_loops
    global complete_list
    global restart_activated
    global restart_nums_collected

    restart_activated = True

    print("\n>>>>>>>>> No match found <<<<<<<<<<")
    print(">>>>>>>>> restart everything <<<<<<<<<<")

    complete_list = []
    break_all_loops = False

    loop_count = 0

    new_set_numbers = set_of_numbers.copy()

    if len(restart_set_collected) > 0:
        for nums_collected in restart_nums_collected:

            new_set_numbers.remove(nums_collected)

            # ===== count total steps for each function and
loop

```



```

# ===== count total steps for each function and loop
count_total_steps()
print(">>>>>>>>> Step: Split into three <<<<<<<<<<")
# =====

if len(set_of_numbers) % 3 == 0:
    global number_of_subsets
    number_of_subsets = len(set_of_numbers) // 3

    # ===== function sum of sets
    sum_of_set()
    # =====

else:
    print("===== Error =====")
    print("The total number of items can't be divided into
3")

def no_match_found():
    global break_all_loops
    break_all_loops = True
    print("\n===== Error =====")
    print("Break this loop")
    print("===== Error =====")

def find_match(start_with_this_num=-1):

    largest_num = new_set_numbers[start_with_this_num]
    new_set_numbers.remove(largest_num)

    global restart_activated
    global restart_set_collected
    global restart_nums_collected

    index_smallest_num = 0

    while len(new_set_numbers) > 0:

        if index_smallest_num >= 1:
            previous_num = new_set_numbers[index_smallest_num -
1]
            skipped_nums = 0

```



```

        collect_numbers = [smallest_number,
difference_nums, largest_num, ]
        new_set_numbers[index_smallest_num] =
smallest_number

        if restart_activated:
            restart_activated = False

            if len(restart_set_collected) > 0:
                for sets_inside_rsc in
restart_set_collected:
                    complete_list.append(sets_inside_rsc)

                    restart_set_collected.append(collect_numbers)
                    restart_nums_collected.append(smallest_number)
                    restart_nums_collected.append(difference_nums)
                    restart_nums_collected.append(largest_num)

                print(f"new set nums before deletion =
{new_set_numbers}")
                print(f"collected numbers: {collect_numbers}")
                new_set_numbers.remove(smallest_number)
                new_set_numbers.remove(difference_nums)
                complete_list.append(collect_numbers)
                print(f"new set nums after deletion =
{new_set_numbers}")
                break
            else:
                print("there is no match found")
                new_set_numbers[index_smallest_num] =
smallest_number
                index_middle_restart = (len(new_set_numbers) + 1) /
2 - 1

                if index_smallest_num > int(index_middle_restart) -
1:
                    if set_of_numbers[start_with_this_num] ==
largest_num:
                        global break_all_loops
                        break_all_loops = True
                        new_set_numbers.append(largest_num)
                        break
                    else:
                        print("activate restart match")
                        no_match_found()
                        restart_match(largest_num)

```

```

        break

    index_smallest_num += 1

def output_error():
    print("\n===== Error =====")
    print(f"Remaining set doesn't match the sum for each
subset: {amount_each_subset}")
    print(f"The sets are: {new_set_numbers}")
    print("===== Error =====")

# ===== Start program

can_be_split_into_three()

if amount_each_subset > -1:

    loop_count = 0

    original_set = set_of_numbers.copy()
    sorting_algorithm()
    new_set_numbers = set_of_numbers.copy()
    print(f"\nset start: {original_set}")
    print(f"set sorted: {new_set_numbers}\n")

    while number_of_subsets > loop_count and not
break_all_loops:
        # ===== count total steps for each function and
loop
        count_total_steps()
        # =====

        if len(new_set_numbers) > 3:
            find_match()
        else:
            if sum(new_set_numbers) == amount_each_subset:

                # ===== count only this function
count_only_when_finding_match += 1
                # =====

                print("\n=====")
                print(f"Sum of Remaining subset:
{new_set_numbers} = {amount_each_subset}")

```


Appendix B:

Link to the GitHub repository containing the python code used in this research paper:

<https://github.com/07231985/3partition>

filename: 3partition_complete_greedy_algorithm.py

```
# Complete Greedy Algorithm for 3 partition problems
# research paper: Possibility of Proving P = NP through 3
partition problems
# created by Glenn Patrick King Ang 12/03/2021
# email: glenn.patrick.king.ang@outlook.com (preferred)
# email: glenn.p.ang@alumni.uts.edu.au (not affiliated, only an
alumni)
# https://github.com/07231985

# sample sets:

set_of_numbers = [20, 23, 25, 30, 49, 45, 27, 30, 30, 40, 23,
18, 55,
                 35, 0, 89, 1, 0, 45, 40, 5, 0, -1, 91, -89,
179, 0, ]

# set_of_numbers = [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9]
# set_of_numbers = [9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1]

# set_of_numbers = [13, 10, 8, 1, 1, 1] # 13 has no match

# set_of_numbers = [9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5,
4, 3, 2, 1, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1,
#           9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5,
4, 3, 2, 1, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1,
#           9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5,
4, 3, 2, 1, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, ]

# set_of_numbers = [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5,
6, 7, 8, 9, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9,
#           1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5,
6, 7, 8, 9, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9,
#           1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5,
6, 7, 8, 9, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, ]

# set_of_numbers = [9, 5, 3, 6, 7, 1, 2, 4, 8]
```

```

# set_of_numbers = [0, 7, 2, 3, 1, 9, 8, 5, 1, 0, 7, 2, 3, 1,
9, 8, 5, 1,
#
0, 7, 2, 3, 1, 9, 8, 5, 1, 0, 7, 2, 3, 1,
9, 8, 5, 1, ]

# number of steps test sets (Section 14):

# section 14.a
# set_of_numbers = [9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1]

# section 14.b
# set_of_numbers = [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, ]

# section 14.c
# set_of_numbers = [9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5,
4, 3, 2, 1, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1,
#
9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5,
4, 3, 2, 1, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1,
#
9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5,
4, 3, 2, 1, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, ]

# section 14.d
# set_of_numbers = [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5,
6, 7, 8, 9, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9,
#
1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5,
6, 7, 8, 9, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9,
#
1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5,
6, 7, 8, 9, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, ]

# section 14.e
# set_of_numbers = [20, 23, 25, 30, 49, 45, 27, 30, 30, 40, 23,
18, 55,
#
35, 0, 89, 1, 0, 45, 40, 5, 0, -1, 91, -89,
179, 0, ]

# section 14.f
# set_of_numbers = [13, 10, 8, 1, 1, 1] # 13 has no match

# section 14.g
# set_of_numbers = [0, 7, 2, 3, 1, 9, 8, 5, 1, 0, 7, 2, 3, 1,
9, 8, 5, 1,
#
0, 7, 2, 3, 1, 9, 8, 5, 1, 0, 7, 2, 3, 1,
9, 8, 5, 1,
#
0, 7, 2, 3, 1, 9, 8, 5, 1, 0, 7, 2, 3, 1,
9, 8, 5, 1,

```



```

#          1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2,
2, 2, 2, 2,
#          2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 3, 3,
3, 3, 3, 3,
#          3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3,
3, 5, 5, 5,
#          5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5,
5, 5, 5, 5,
#          7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7,
7, 7, 7, 7,
#          7, 7, 7, 8, 8, 8, 8, 8, 8, 8, 8, 8, 8, 8,
8, 8, 8, 8,
#          8, 8, 8, 8, 8, 8, 9, 9, 9, 9, 9, 9, 9, 9,
9, 9, 9, 9,
#          9, 9, 9, 9, 9, 9, 9, 9, 9]

```

```

original_set_numbers = set_of_numbers.copy()
new_set_numbers = set_of_numbers.copy()
amount_each_subset = -1
break_all_loops = False
count_steps = 0
number_of_subsets = 0
collect_subsets = []

def count_total_steps():
    global count_steps
    count_steps += 1

def sum_of_set():
    # ===== count total steps for each function and loop
    count_total_steps()
    # =====

    print(">>>>>>>>> Step: Sum of sets <<<<<<<<<\n")

    sum_nums = sum(set_of_numbers)
    print(f"Number of subsets: {number_of_subsets}")

    if sum_nums % number_of_subsets == 0:
        global amount_each_subset
        amount_each_subset = sum_nums // number_of_subsets
        print(f"Total sum = {sum_nums}")
        print(f"Amount each subset = {amount_each_subset}")

```



```

        new_set_numbers_x.remove(new_set_numbers[x_index])
        new_set_numbers_y = new_set_numbers_x.copy()
        print(f"\n===== start program
with x: {x}")

        while len(new_set_numbers_y) > 1:
            print(f"\ny subset length is
{len(new_set_numbers_y)}")
            print(f"y subset = {new_set_numbers_y}")
            y = new_set_numbers_y[0]
            print(f"\n===== start program
with x: {x} and y: {y}")
            new_set_numbers_y.remove(new_set_numbers_y[0])

            for z in new_set_numbers_y:

                # ===== count total steps
                count_total_steps()
                # =====

                print(f"combination: x: {x} y:{y} z:{z}")
                combination_sum = x + y + z

                if combination_sum == amount_each_subset:
                    collect_combination = [x, y, z]
                    print("\n***** ")
                    print(f"match found: sum of combination
{collect_combination} = {amount_each_subset}")
                    print("***** \n")

                    collect_subsets.append(collect_combination)

print("\n***** Results
*****")
print(f"original set: {original_set_numbers}")
print(f"total number of elements inside the set:
{len(original_set_numbers)}")
print(f"\nnumber of subsets: {number_of_subsets}")
print(f"Total sum of the entire set: {amount_each_subset *
number_of_subsets}")
print(f"The amount for each subset is: {amount_each_subset}")

print(f"\ncollected list of all possible subsets:
{collect_subsets}")
print(f"Total number of all possible subsets collected:
{len(collect_subsets)}")

```

```

print(f"\nTotal steps for finding all possible subsets:
{count_steps}")
print("*****
*****")

#
*****
*****
# ***** Finding Subsets
*****
#
*****
*****

print("\n\n===== start looking for subsets")

set_numbers_complete = set_of_numbers.copy()
loop_count_for = 0
collect_sets = []
count_steps_finding_subset = 0

set_x = collect_subsets.copy()

for x in collect_subsets:

    loop_count_for += 1

    print(f"\n===== starting subsets program with
the for loop: {loop_count_for}")

    find_subsets = x.copy()

    set_x.remove(find_subsets)

    set_numbers_complete = set_of_numbers.copy()
    set_numbers_complete.remove(find_subsets[0])
    set_numbers_complete.remove(find_subsets[1])
    set_numbers_complete.remove(find_subsets[2])

    collect_sets.append(find_subsets)

    for y in set_x:

        find_y_subsets = y.copy()

        if len(set_numbers_complete) > 0:

```

```

        count_total_steps()
        count_steps_finding_subset += 1

        # print(f"available subset: {find_y_subsets} and
the remaining set = {set_numbers_complete}")

        if find_y_subsets[0] in set_numbers_complete:
            set_numbers_complete.remove(find_y_subsets[0])
            if find_y_subsets[1] in set_numbers_complete:
set_numbers_complete.remove(find_y_subsets[1])

                if find_y_subsets[2] in
set_numbers_complete:
set_numbers_complete.remove(find_y_subsets[2])
                    collect_sets.append(find_y_subsets)

                        # print("\n*****")
")
                        # print(f"match found: removing
combination {find_y_subsets} new set: {set_numbers_complete}")
                        # print("*****
\n")

                            else:

set_numbers_complete.append(find_y_subsets[0])
set_numbers_complete.append(find_y_subsets[1])
                                else:

set_numbers_complete.append(find_y_subsets[0])
                                    else:
                                        break

                            if len(set_numbers_complete) == 0:
                                break
                            else:
                                collect_sets = []

                                # print("\n***** ")
                                # print(f"resetting collected sets: {collect_sets}")

```

```

# print("***** \n")

print("\n***** Finding
Subsets Output *****")
print(f"found possible subsets: {collect_subsets}")
print(f"\nThe complete list of subsets: {collect_sets}")
print(f"total steps for finding the complete list of subsets
only: {count_steps_finding_subset}")

print(f"\ntotal steps for finding all possible subsets:
{count_steps - count_steps_finding_subset}")
print(f"total steps for finding all possible subsets + finding
the {number_of_subsets} subset(s): {count_steps}")
print("*****
*****")

```